

A Comparative Study of Non-performing Assets in Selected Public Sector Banks and Private Sector Banks in India

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Chirag P. Surti

Faculty Member
Dept Of Accounting &
Financial Management
Faculty Of Commerce, The
Maharaja Sayajirao
University Of Baroda,
Vadodara, Gujarat, India

Abstract

The banking sector plays a crucial role in the economic growth of a country, particularly in a developing nation like India, where financial institutions act as key intermediaries in mobilizing and allocating resources efficiently. One of the major challenges faced by banks in recent years is the rising level of Non-Performing Assets (NPAs), which adversely affects profitability, liquidity, and overall financial stability. This study focuses on the analysis and comparison of Gross Non-Performing Assets (GNPA) and Net Non-Performing Assets (NNPA) ratios of selected Public Sector Banks and Private Sector Banks in India over the period from 2020–21 to 2024–25.

The primary objective of the study is to examine trends in NPAs, evaluate the effectiveness of credit risk management practices, and assess the impact of regulatory measures on asset quality. The research is based on secondary data collected from annual reports of banks and publications from recognized financial institutions. Statistical tools such as mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, and ANOVA have been used for analysis and hypothesis testing.

The findings of the study reveal a consistent decline in GNPA and NNPA ratios across both public and private sector banks, indicating an improvement in asset quality over the study period. However, public sector banks were found to have higher average NPA ratios compared to private sector banks, reflecting relatively weaker credit risk management in earlier years. Private sector banks demonstrated better stability and efficiency in managing NPAs. The ANOVA results confirm that there is a statistically significant difference in NPA ratios among the selected banks.

The study concludes that regulatory reforms, improved credit appraisal systems, and effective recovery mechanisms have contributed significantly to the reduction of NPAs in the Indian banking sector. The research highlights the need for banks to adopt advanced risk management strategies and proactive measures to further minimize NPAs and enhance overall performance.

Keywords

Non-performing Assets, Public Sector Banks, Private Sector Banks.

Introduction

Banking plays a crucial role in the efficient utilization of national assets through lending, investing, and facilitating the transfer of money both within the country and internationally. This role is especially significant in developing countries like India, where challenges such as poverty, limited funds, and a lack of entrepreneurship persist. Additionally, there are issues like inter-district and inter-zone inequalities, resulting in the uneven allocation of capital.

Public Sector Banks (PSBs) serve as key financial intermediaries in such contexts, managing the flow of funds and ensuring financial expansion through appropriate regulatory practices. They follow specific rules that align with the prevailing economic circumstances of the nation. Therefore, the environment in which these banks operate is vital, as it can either foster their growth or hinder their operations.

Banks must perform their functions in accordance with the monetary and credit policies set by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI). These policies serve as operational controls and significantly influence the actions of both Public and Private Sector Banks.

In India, Public Sector Banks, which are primarily government-owned, have a significant responsibility in promoting inclusive growth and financial stability. On the other hand,

Private Sector Banks, which are owned by private entities, often operate with different objectives and strategies but are equally important in fostering competition and innovation within the financial sector.

For the continued existence and success of Public Sector Banks, the management of Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) is crucial. This challenge, along with adherence to RBI's financial and credit plans, impacts the stability and performance of both Public and Private Sector Banks in India.

Objective of study

1. To understand the concept of Non-Performing Assets (NPAs),
2. To analyze and compare the trends in Gross Non-Performing Assets (GNPA) and Net Non-Performing Assets (Net NPA) ratios between selected Public Sector Banks and Private Sector Banks in India
3. To assess the impact of regulatory frameworks and corrective measures on the reduction of Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) in the banking sector.
4. To evaluate the effectiveness of credit risk management and recovery mechanisms in selected Public and Private Sector Banks and their influence on asset quality, as reflected by GNPA and Net NPA ratios.

Review of Literature

The management of Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) in banks has garnered significant attention in both academic and industry research, given its critical role in maintaining the stability of the banking system. Various reports and circulars issued by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), publications like IBA Bulletins, RBI guidelines, and PSB handbooks have provided valuable insights into the evolving challenges and solutions for managing NPAs. The existing literature consistently emphasizes that high NPAs adversely impact the profitability, productivity, and reputation of these banks, thereby stressing the need for efficient management strategies.

1. Akshita Chauhan, Dr. Sunil Kumar Roy, Dr. Shuchi Singhal (2025) in their research paper titled "A Systematic Literature Review On Non-Performing Assets In Public Sector Banks" concluded that Indian commercial banks are grappling with challenges posed by non-performing assets (NPAs), as they significantly impact the financial stability and performance of these banks. Moreover, adherence to Basel standards for maintaining high liquidity is imperative for banks. Therefore, addressing NPA issues is crucial to safeguard financial performance and preserve the reputation of banks. Both the RBI and the Government of India have taken measures to mitigate the volume of NPAs in commercial banks. Researchers have conducted a comprehensive review of literature from various global and Indian sources, identifying gaps in existing analyses and suggesting future research directions to explore novel approaches for managing NPAs in Indian commercial banks.
2. Swetha C and Dr. S .Rosaline Jayanthi (2024) : in their research paper titled "A Comparative Study on Non Performing Assets (NPA) of SBI and HDFC Bank" they concluded that The analysis reveals that while SBI maintains strong profitability despite high NPAs, it faces potential concerns about adequate provisioning. In contrast, HDFC Bank experiences a significant negative impact on profitability due to high NPAs, with both GNPA and NNPA adversely affecting key financial metrics. Effective NPA management is crucial for both banks, but the challenges and outcomes vary.
3. Rachan Sareen (2023) in the research paper titled concluded that "Analysis of bank specific factors of non-performing assets of select commercial banks" Non-performing assets are a major cause of concern for banks worldwide, and their impact on a bank's profitability and financial stability cannot be overstated. The factors that contribute to NPA can vary across banks. There are several bank-specific factors and macroeconomic factors whose relationship with nonperforming assets has been investigated in previous studies. The present study empirically tested the relationship between variables representing different parameters of CAMELS approach and non performing asset for each of six years from 2017 to 2022. In the present study, the R-squared values for the regression models were found to be high, indicating that a significant portion of the variance in the net NPA ratio can be attributed to the independent variables considered in the analysis. It is important that banks monitor various financial indicators to manage and mitigate their credit risk. While government initiatives are important in addressing the issue of non-performing assets in the banking sector, it is also important to acknowledge that NPAs can be attributed to poor credit discipline. This includes inefficient underwriting criteria, inadequate due diligence or collateral and lack of proper monitoring of borrowers' creditworthiness. To effectively tackle the issue of NPAs, it is necessary to implement internal controls and responsible lending practices within the banking sector. The automation and digitisation of processes can

improve the efficiency and accuracy of credit assessments, while also ensuring better risk management and reduction of NPAs.

Methodology

The primary data for this research is collected from secondary sources, such as the annual reports of the banks, financial statements, and relevant databases like the Indian Banking Association (IBA). Descriptive statistics, including mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation, are used to summarize the trends in NPAs across different banks.

Period of the study

The paper discusses management of non-performing assets of selected public sector banks and Private sector banks in India from period of 2020-21 to 2024-25.

Concept of Non-Performing Assets

Assets of the banks are classified as performing assets and non-performing assets (NPAs) for the purpose of income recognition. An asset becomes non-performing when it ceases to generate income for banks. Assets returning income on a continuous basis is called performing asset. A non-performing asset would be an advance where:

1. Interest and/or instalment of principal remain overdue for a period of more than 90 days in respect of a term loan,
2. The account remains 'out of order' for a period of more than 90 days, in respect of an Overdraft/Cash Credit (OD/CC),
3. The bill remains overdue for a period of more than 90 days in case of bills purchased and discounted,
4. Interest and/or instalment of principal remains overdue for two harvest seasons but for a period not exceeding two half years in the case of an advance granted for agricultural purposes, and
5. Any amount to be received remains overdue for a period of more than 90 days in respect of other account.

An account is treated as 'out of order' when the outstanding balance continuously exceeds the sanctioned limit or drawing power. This situation indicates irregularity in the account and is a Key criterion for identifying potential non-performing assets.

An amount is considered 'overdue' if it is not paid on the due date fixed by the bank under any credit facility. The concept of overdue plays a crucial role in asset classification and monitoring of credit discipline

Banks are advised by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) to recognize income on an accrual basis in respect of performing assets, whereas income on non-performing assets (NPAs) should be recognized on a cash basis. This ensures a prudent and realistic reflection of bank income.

Classification of Assets (Advances):

Standard Assets:

A standard asset is one which does not disclose any significant problem and carries only normal risk associated with the business. Such assets are considered performing assets (PAs) and do not require special monitoring.

Sub-standard Assets:

A sub-standard asset is one which has remained a non-performing asset (NPA) for a period less than or equal to 12 months. These assets exhibit well-defined credit weaknesses, and there is uncertainty regarding full recovery due to inadequacy of security or decline in the borrower's financial position. This category indicates a distinct possibility of some loss if corrective measures are not taken

Doubtful Assets:

An asset is classified as doubtful if it remains in the sub-standard category for more than 12 months. Such assets possess all the weaknesses of sub-standard assets, with an added degree of uncertainty regarding full recovery. Collection or liquidation of such loans becomes highly questionable based on existing conditions

Loss Assets:

A loss asset is one where loss has been identified by the bank, its internal or external auditors, or during inspection by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), but the amount has not yet been written off. These assets are considered uncollectible and of such little value that their continuation as bankable assets is not justified, although some marginal recovery may still be possible.

Loss asset should be written off, if loss assets are permitted to remain in the books for any reason, 100% of the outstanding should be provided for.

Table 1. Provisioning Norms:

	Category of Advances	Provision (%)
(A)	Standard Advances (Assets)	
	Direct advances to agriculture and SME sectors	0.25
	Advances to commercial, real estate sector	1.00
	Advance to commercial real estate sector- Residential Housing Sector	0.75
	All others	0.40
(B)	Sub-standard Advances	
	Secured Exposures	15
	Unsecured Exposures	25
	Unsecured Exposures in respect of infrastructure loan account where certain safeguards such as Escrow Accounts are available	20
(C)	Doubtful Advances	
	Unsecured portion	100
	Secured portion:	25
	Up to 1 year	40
	More than 1 year & Up to 3 years	100
(D)	Loss Assets	100

(Source: www.rbi.org.in)

Stressed assets: Stressed assets are an important indicator of the overall health of the banking system. They represent the total burden of problematic loans in the banking sector. Stressed assets comprise of :

1. Non-Performing Assets
2. Restructured Assets
3. Written-off Assets

Restructured Assets: It includes those advances where the defaulting borrowers have been given another opportunity to repay the advances. This opportunity may be in the form of charging interest at reduced rate, extended time period for repayment.

Written off assets: Written off assets are those advances which the bank does not count its assets through the borrower owes it. It does not mean that the borrower is pardoned or get exempted from payment.

Reasons of Non-performing assets in Banks

External Causes:

1. Destruction of assets due to natural calamities.
2. Industry recession affecting business operations.
3. Factory closure from strikes or court orders.
4. Adverse government policies increasing costs or reducing sales.
5. Decrease in demand from factors like environmental regulations, changing fashions, or shifting consumer preferences.

Internal Causes:

Management Issues:

1. Fraudulent activities by business partners or directors.
2. Willful defaults by the company.

3. Poor organizational setup and lack of control.
4. Disputes among company partners or directors.

Marketing Issues:

1. Limited product range and market offerings.
2. Inadequate distribution channels.
3. Irregular product delivery.
4. Incorrect pricing strategies.

Financing Issues:

1. Insufficient financial resources.
2. High-cost borrowing from external sources.
3. Misuse of funds for unproductive activities.
4. Faulty costing and pricing strategies.
5. Increased production costs reducing profitability.

Production Issues:

1. Outdated or inappropriate technology used in production.
2. Low labour productivity.
3. Inadequate quality control measures.
4. Poor production planning and control.
5. Inferior quality of finished goods leading to poor sales.
6. Frequent machine breakdowns causing production delays.

Gross Non-performing Assets Ratio of Selected Public Sector and Private Sector Banks in India

The Gross Non-Performing Asset (GNPA) ratio is an important indicator of the asset quality and financial performance of banks. A higher GNPA ratio reflects poor recovery of loans and higher credit risk, whereas a lower GNPA ratio indicates better asset management and financial Stability.

Percentage of Gross Non-Performing Assets of Selected

Public Sector Banks & Private Sector Banks in India

Table 2

Years	Public Sector Banks (in%)				Private Sector Banks (in%)				(Source :
	Bank of Baroda	Bank of India	Punjab National Bank	State Bank of India	Axis Bank	ICICI Bank	IndusInd Bank	Kotak Mahindra Bank	
2020-21	9.43	15.46	15.49	5.16	4.12	5.64	2.73	3.32	
2021-22	6.96	10.84	12.70	4.10	3.20	3.95	2.31	2.39	
2022-23	3.91	7.76	9.31	2.84	2.20	3.06	2.00	1.80	
2023-24	2.99	5.18	6.03	2.28	1.57	2.36	1.95	1.40	
2024-25	2.30	3.35	4.09	1.85	1.39	1.80	3.20	1.44	
Average	5.12	8.52	9.52	3.25	2.50	3.36	2.44	2.07	
SD P	2.68	4.29	4.18	1.22	1.03	1.35	0.47	0.72	
C.V	52.37	50.36	43.91	37.58	41.25	40.06	19.35	34.73	

www.iba.org.in)

The table presents the percentage of Gross Non-Performing Assets (GNPA) of selected public sector banks and private sector banks in India for the period 2020–21 to 2024–25. The data shows a clear declining trend in GNPA ratios for most banks over the study period.

In the case of public sector banks, Bank of Baroda reduced its GNPA from 9.43% in 2020–21 to 2.30% in 2024–25, indicating a significant improvement in asset quality. Bank of India recorded one of the highest GNPA levels at 15.46% in 2020–21, which gradually declined to 3.35% by 2024–25. Similarly, Punjab National Bank reduced its GNPA from 15.49% to 4.09% during the same period. State Bank of India maintained relatively lower GNPA levels among public sector banks, declining from 5.16% to 1.85%.

In private sector banks, the GNPA ratios were generally lower throughout the period. Axis Bank reduced its GNPA from 4.12% in 2020–21 to 1.39% in 2024–25, while ICICI Bank improved from 5.64% to 1.80%. IndusInd Bank initially showed a decline in GNPA but experienced a slight increase in 2024–25. Kotak Mahindra Bank maintained relatively low GNPA levels throughout the study period, indicating better asset quality management

The statistical analysis further strengthens this observation. The average GNPA ratio was highest for Punjab National Bank (9.52%), followed by Bank of India (8.52%) and Bank of Baroda (5.12%), indicating relatively higher levels of non-performing assets among these public sector banks during the study period. On the other hand, Kotak Mahindra Bank recorded the lowest average GNPA ratio (2.07%), reflecting better asset quality management. The standard deviation indicates the variation in GNPA ratios over the years. Public sector banks such as Bank of India (4.29) and Punjab National Bank (4.18) showed higher fluctuations compared to Private sector Banks

The coefficient of variation (CV) shows the stability of GNPA ratios. Bank of Baroda recorded the highest CV (52.34%), indicating higher variability in its GNPA ratio during the study period. In contrast, IndusInd Bank recorded the lowest CV (19.27%), which indicates more stability and consistency in maintaining its asset quality.

Table 2.1 ANOVA – GROSS NON-PERFORMING ASSETS RATIO

ANOVA						
<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	293.6632	7	41.95189	5.572866	0.000291	2.312741
Within Groups	240.8923	32	7.527884			
Total	534.5555	39				

The calculated F-statistic value is 5.572866, whereas the critical F value at the 5% level of significance is 2.312741. Since the calculated F value (5.572866) is greater than the critical F value (2.312741), the result indicates a statistically significant difference.

The P-value is 0.000291, which is much less than the significance level of 0.05. This further confirms that the difference among the banks' GNPA ratios is statistically significant.

Since the calculated F value exceeds the critical F value and the P-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the Gross Non-Performing Assets ratios among the selected public sector and private sector banks during the period 2020–21 to 2024–25. This indicates that the banks differ in their effectiveness in managing non-performing assets.

Net Non-performing Assets Ratio of Selected Public Sector and Private Sector Banks in India

Net Non-Performing Assets (Net NPA) ratio refers to the proportion of loans and advances that have become non-performing after deducting provisions made by the bank. It indicates the actual credit risk faced by banks. A lower Net NPA ratio reflects better asset quality and efficient loan recovery performance of the bank. On the other hand, a higher Net NPA ratio indicates weak credit management and a higher possibility of loan defaults.

Percentage of Net Non-Performing Assets of Selected

Public Sector Banks & Private Sector Banks in India.

Table 3

Years	Public Sector Banks (in%)				Private Sector Banks (in %)			
	Bank of Baroda	Bank of India	Punjab National Bank	State Bank of India	Axis Bank	ICICI Bank	Indusind Bank	Kotak Mahindra Bank
2020-21	3.09	3.35	5.73	1.50	1.05	1.14	0.69	1.21
2021-22	1.72	2.34	4.89	1.02	0.73	0.76	0.64	0.64
2022-23	0.89	1.66	2.72	0.67	0.39	0.48	0.59	0.37

2023-24	0.68	1.22	0.73	0.57	0.31	0.42	0.57	0.34
2024-25	0.58	0.82	0.40	0.47	0.33	0.39	0.95	0.31
Average	1.39	1.88	2.89	0.85	0.56	0.64	0.69	0.57
SDVP	0.94	0.89	2.14	0.38	0.29	0.28	0.14	0.34
CV	67.63	47.34	74.09	44.71	51.79	43.75	20.29	59.65

(Source : www.iba.org.in)

The table presents the percentage of Net Non-Performing Assets of selected public sector and private sector banks in India for the period 2020-21 to 2024-25.

Public Sector Banks

Bank of Baroda recorded an average Net NPA ratio of 1.39 percent with a standard deviation of 0.94 and a coefficient of variation of 67.63 percent, indicating moderate fluctuations during the study period.

Bank of India shows an average Net NPA ratio of 1.88 percent with a standard deviation of 0.89 and a coefficient of variation of 47.34 percent, reflecting relatively stable performance compared to some other public sector banks.

Punjab National Bank recorded the highest average Net NPA ratio among the selected banks at 2.89 percent along with the highest standard deviation of 2.14 and coefficient of variation of 74.09 percent, which indicates significant fluctuations and comparatively weaker asset quality.

State Bank of India maintained a lower average Net NPA ratio of 0.85 percent with a standard deviation of 0.38 and a coefficient of variation of 44.71 percent, indicating comparatively better asset management.

Private Sector Banks

Axis Bank recorded an average Net NPA ratio of 0.56 percent with a standard deviation of 0.29 and a coefficient of variation of 51.79 percent, showing moderate variation during the study period.

ICICI Bank reported an average Net NPA ratio of 0.64 percent with a standard deviation of 0.28 and a coefficient of variation of 43.75 percent, indicating relatively stable asset quality.

IndusInd Bank recorded an average Net NPA ratio of 0.69 percent with the lowest standard deviation of 0.14 and coefficient of variation of 20.29 percent, showing the most consistent performance. Kotak Mahindra Bank shows an average Net NPA ratio of 0.57 percent with a standard deviation of 0.34 and coefficient of variation of 59.65 percent, indicating moderate variability.

Table 3.1 ANOVA – NET NON-PERFORMING ASSETS RATIO

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	24.3318	7	3.475971	3.316434	0.009082	2.312741
Within Groups	33.53936	32	1.048105			
Total	57.87116	39				

The calculated F-value is 3.316434, while the critical F value (F crit) is 2.312741 at 5% level of significance. . Since the calculated F-value (3.316434) is greater than the F critical value (2.312741), it indicates that there is a significant difference among the groups.

The P-value obtained from the ANOVA test is 0.009082, which is less than the significance level of 0.05. This further confirms that the difference in Net NPA Ratios among the selected banks is statistically significant.

Based on the ANOVA results, the Null Hypothesis H₀ is rejected and the Alternative Hypothesis H₁ is accepted, because the calculated F Value (3.316434) is greater than the critical F Value (2.312741) and the P. Value(0.009082) is less than 0.05

Therefore , it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the Net NPA ratio among the selected Public sector banks and Private sector banks during the study period. This indicates that the banks differ in their efficiency in managing non-performing assets .

Conclusion

The data indicates that public sector banks initially had significantly higher GNPA ratios compared to private sector banks. However, a consistent decline in GNPA levels over the years suggests that various corrective measures, improved credit monitoring, and better recovery mechanisms have been effective.

Private sector banks maintained lower GNPA ratios during the study period, reflecting stronger credit risk management practices and more efficient operational systems. The gradual decline in GNPA across both sectors indicates an overall improvement in the financial health of the banking system.

The statistical measures also show that Punjab National Bank and Bank of India had higher average GNPA ratios, while Kotak Mahindra Bank and IndusInd Bank maintained lower averages and greater stability. This indicates that private sector banks generally demonstrated stronger asset quality management compared to public sector Banks

Therefore, the study concludes that although public sector banks faced higher non-performing assets in earlier years, continuous reforms, stricter credit monitoring, and improved recovery mechanisms have contributed to the reduction of GNPA ratios in the Indian banking sector.

From the analysis, it is observed that private sector banks maintain lower Net NPA ratios compared to public sector banks, indicating better asset quality and credit risk management. Among public sector banks, State Bank of India shows relatively better performance, while Punjab National Bank records the highest Net NPA ratio and variability. In the private sector, IndusInd Bank demonstrates the most stable performance with the lowest coefficient of variation. Overall, the study indicates that private sector banks have performed more efficiently in controlling Net NPAs during the study period.

Suggestions for the future Study

1. **Establish a robust verification system:** Banks must implement a system to ensure that funds raised through loans are utilized according to the sanctioned proposals, with verification by responsible bank officials.
2. **Comprehensive asset verification reports:** The verification report must include detailed descriptions of assets, including their make, supplier, age, and remaining economic life, to assess their performance.
3. **Account for asset age and life cycle:** Reports should provide a clear basis for determining the age and remaining economic life of assets to ensure accurate performance monitoring.
4. **Yearly provision based on asset life:** Banks should create a provision schedule that matches the economic life of the financed assets, ensuring that the loan amount is adequately provided for each year.
5. **Pro-rata provisioning on standard assets:** In line with the economic life of the assets, banks should make provisions for standard assets on a pro-rata basis, even for well-performing loans.
6. **Temporary impact on profitability:** While provisioning will initially affect profitability, it can strengthen the bank's financial position and allow for smoother management of NPAs in the long term.
7. **Use provisions to cover potential NPAs:** In case an asset turns NPA, banks should have sufficient provision in place from the start to cover the potential bad debt.
8. **Improved provisions to boost bank ratings:** Strong provisions against NPAs may improve the bank's ratings by showcasing its ability to manage credit risk efficiently.
9. **Reconsider the practice of write-offs for smaller amounts:** Banks should review the practice of writing off small amounts (e.g., Rs. 100,000 or less) and focus on recovering every amount financed, regardless of the size of the outstanding balance.
10. **Systematic assessment of non-loan assets:** Banks must establish a procedure to regularly assess the performance of all types of assets, not just loans, and take appropriate action when non-performance is identified.

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